

METHODS FOR CULTIVATING ENGLISH WRITING SKILLS

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Annotation: Writing is a crucial part of English language instruction. Writing enables us to transmit information to future generations while also preserving it for millennia. Through it, additional knowledge is shared. Writing is a speech activity that we need to learn, as was already said. Calculation and coding of written information are the essential elements of speaking action. In this article, there are thoughts and opinions about learning English, and in particular, this article will focus on improving your writing skills in English.

Keywords: English language, educational methods, formation of written speech, writing ability, improvement of knowledge.

Writing is seen as a collection of abilities in a competency-based approach, encompassing the significance of text creation, spelling, punctuation, and grammar. Writing instruction, in the words of McLaughlin, "requires students to construct a series of linked tasks and their components." As opposed to compositional principles, a whole-language viewpoint views writing as a meaning-making process driven by purpose and audience.

One of the most important skills that English as a second language learners and professionals need to develop is writing. Unlike speaking, writing is about maintaining your language over time. Errors in spelling, grammar and word choice are immediately noticed. Even if a student understands the subject matter, poor writing can lead to poor grades, even though literacy skills are not a measure of intelligence or understanding. If you send error-filled emails in a professional context, they might think you're careless and untrustworthy.

Writing skills help you communicate clearly with others and produce resources that are useful in business. Written communication skills are essential, even for non-writing oriented careers, from job applications to daily tasks to paperwork. Effective writing skills help professionals in any business stand out from employers, promote their interests, and complete tasks faster. Writing skills are a crucial component of communication. Compared to talking to someone in person or over the phone, writing allows you to get your message across to a much larger audience. You may be required to create a report, plan or strategy for the work; grant application or press release for a volunteer position; or you may want to use a blog to share your thoughts with the world.

Despite much discussion about writing skills, many books do not focus enough on exercises to develop them. In textbooks for language learning, a lot of attention and space is devoted to exercises and tasks aimed at developing listening and speaking skills.

Until the 80s of the last century, the attention to writing skills in foreign language classes was very weak, and writing official letters, forms and others did not have a small place in the language. But with the development of the Internet, the development of writing skills began to take off.

Neuropsychological research reflected in new age research emphasizes that all language skills (writing, speaking, listening, reading) are interrelated. It is shown that the development of writing skills in foreign language classes consists of two stages: Stage 1: distribution, preparation, management of exercises, evaluation of other skills (listening, reading, speaking, grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation). The second stage is the stage of formation of writing skills.

Reading is the ability to understand the meaning of language information given to a person and to accept this information. In writing, students must create meaning and their own language. Writing is difficult for everyone, even native speakers. In almost all programs for various educational institutions that teach foreign languages, writing is called a means of education, not a goal. At all levels of education, writing plays a supporting role in the development of speaking, listening comprehension and reading skills. Writing is a learning tool and has a variety of functions in the high school curriculum. For example, the main goal of the first stage of education is to teach writing, because it is during this period that students learn to write beautifully and identify vowels. These skills are important building blocks for the development of reading and writing.

In the second stage of training, attention to spelling increases, which is associated with the accumulation of new linguistic information during the writing process. The development of written speech also serves as a means of developing oral communication skills. Writing also plays an important role in education, as it is used by students as a means of interpreting and planning independent language work, particularly reading. Writing serves as a transitional period in the production of other speech acts. If we write down what we read, the thought of the other is preserved in our minds and properly preserved by writing.

The advantages of dialogue journal writing are generally individualization of writing instruction, use of writing and reading for authentic communication, development of students' process orientation, bridging the gap between speaking and writing, students' real goals for reading and writing. helps to raise awareness about A blank page can be intimidating to writers of all skill levels. Determine the structure of your essay in advance so that you have a framework to work from. There should be an introduction, a few body paragraphs that support your thesis, and a conclusion.

Also, even if you are familiar with a term, it may not be used in your writing. Deliberate use of newly learned terminology is one way to expand your vocabulary. The next time you use it in writing a sentence, it will be easier to use the term. Another option is to use a thesaurus to find synonyms for your chosen sentences. Be careful not to choose strange words that don't make sense in your text or in your original sentence.

Preparatory exercises - such exercises are not specifically designed for writing skills, but serve to form future writing skills. For example: Working on vocabulary, expanding it, strengthening it, activating existing knowledge, strengthening phrases, doing exercises in correct writing. Such exercises can also be done as a game. The word chain game (Wortschlange) is especially popular in schools, and many foreign language teachers make good use of it. Such games can be played both in the plenum and in groups. Organization in the form of a competition is also very effective. Increases students' motivation.

Exercises for creative and free writing - these types of exercises require free text creation without text samples. It can also be understood as personal writing. The creator of the text reflects his thoughts and feelings in his short text. Such exercises include

associogram, clustering, hypothesis generation using audio, visual or verbal prompts. mentions that it can also be the product of the thoughts of the participants of a team [4]. He emphasizes that this form of writing motivates students, encourages weak students, and helps overcome the fear of writing. For example, a group consisting of several students The group of students is given some interesting pictures. They can be taken from newspapers, magazines or comics. The pictures are mixed up and distributed to the students. Each student gets four pictures. They try to make a story using them.

Exercises related to authentic communicative processes - such exercises are exercises focused on real processes that occur in our lives, and can be greeting cards, letters, reports, forms, and the like. The main components of writing are addressee, writing method and addressee. It is very important for whom the text or letter is being written. Examples of such exercises include making cards for birthdays or holidays, verbalizing graphics or diagrams.

In conclusion, if you want to write something, try to focus on spelling. You have to keep practicing. Otherwise, it will be very difficult to remember the correct spelling of each word. Without a doubt, you will become a skilled writer and if you can write properly, you can develop your writing skills without difficulty. The next step in the revision process is to discover the most accurate and reliable terminology that expresses the ideas clearly and concisely. Make sure there are no errors in grammar, spelling or formatting that would divert the reader's attention away from what you are saying.

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